

STUDY OF THE INTERPHASE IN EPOXY/BASALT FIBRE COMPOSITES BY DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The viscoelastic properties of modified unidirectional epoxy basalt fibre composites were investigated. Composites with 30% wt and 70% wt of fibres were analyzed, longitudinally and transversally. Each composite was performed with three differently treated basalt fibres in order to determine the sensitivity and applicability of cooperativity to the interphase analysis. A cooperativity analysis of the composites was carried out on storage modulus (E') master curves obtained from dynamic mechanical analysis. The temperature sensitivity of the horizontal logarithmic shift factors (cooperativity), obtained from E' data, was found to vary with the sizing

used to pretreat the basalt fibres. Composites with high fibre weight fractions showed more reliable cooperativity response than those with low fibre weight fractions. Furthermore, composites with high weight fractions analyzed longitudinally and transversally show the same cooperativity behaviour for the different treated fibre composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre/matrix interphase has outstanding influence on the composite performance. The nature of the interphase is crucial in determining composites behaviour at the required mechanical, thermal and chemical conditions. However, a comprehensive understanding of the role the interphase region plays is still under study.

There have been many authors that predicted the properties of the fibre/matrix interphase using data from dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). Lewis and Nielsen [1] studied the shear modulus of an A-glass bead filled epoxy composite in comparison to an unfilled epoxy sample. It was observed that the relative shear modulus increased with increasing volume fraction of filler and decreasing particle size. They also examined the viscoelastic response of glass fillers treated with different coupling agents. No noticeable effects of varying coupling agents were observed in the shear storage modulus curves. However, the shear loss modulus and damping ($\tan \delta$) curves varied significantly depending on the coupling agent that was used.

Other authors [2] argue that the changes (broadening) in $\tan \delta$ curves due to the incorporation of small diameter alumina particles to a sulfonated polystyrene ionomer are consequence of the polymer/filler interaction degree at the interface. Even more, they state that strong polymer–filler interactions will decrease the mobility and free volume of the polymer chains near the particle surface. Moreover, Eisenberg and Tsagaropoulos [3, 4] theorized that two distinct regions of restricted mobility exist near the filler/polymer interface. The polymer chains nearest to the filler particle are tightly bound and are so highly restricted in mobility, so that they cannot participate in any transitions that are measurable by DMA. Beyond these tightly bound chains are loosely bound chains. These are more restricted in mobility when compared to the bulk polymer phase, but not as restricted as the tightly bound chains. If this model is correct then the differences in the damping curves of composite materials can be attributed to viscoelastic changes in the interphase region surrounding the filler particle.

Jensen et al. [5] used the concept of cooperativity to model the viscoelastic response of epoxy/E-glass fibre composites. The cooperativity analysis required the generation of master curves of the storage modulus in the frequency domain using the time-temperature-superposition procedure and data obtained from DMA. Ngai and Plazek [6] developed an empirical expression (Eq. 1) for determining the coupling parameter (n) of bulk polymers using cooperativity analysis.

$$(1 - n) \log a_T = \frac{-C1(T - T_g)/T_g}{C2 + (T - T_g)/T_g} \quad (1)$$

A Williams, Landel, and Ferry (WLF) type of equation was found, with the temperature normalized by T_g and the presence of the coupling parameter (n). This latter can theoretically vary between 0 and 1. Ngai and Plazek also determine the statistical solutions to $C1$ and $C2$ constants to be equal to 5.49 and 0.141, respectively; being universally used for a wide variety of bulk polymers.

Ngai and Roland [7] provided a molecular interpretation of cooperativity motion. They proposed that a relatively high level of intermolecular interactions increases the breadth of the distribution of relaxation times in a polymer. Under the dense conditions of the solid state the

polymer is in close contact with neighboring chains. When thermal energy is raised, a segmental motion begins to occur at T_g and some of the segments cannot relax without involving non-bonded units in the vicinity. The constraining effect due to neighboring chains slows down the overall relaxation time depending on the volume of the cooperating unity. The coupled segmental relaxations of the polymer chains obviously do not occur at the same time or rate throughout the sample given the heterogeneity of all of the polymer parameters. This leads, phenomenologically, to an increase in the breadth of the distribution of relaxation times. A higher degree of intermolecular coupling and constraints from neighboring segments will increase the amount of cooperative segmental motion required in the transition from the glassy to the rubbery state. In other words, the segmental motion of neighboring segments is correlated to a greater degree. Polymers with a high amount of cooperativity have viscoelastic properties that exhibit steeper temperature dependence in the glass transition region.

The steepness index (S), which is the slope at $T = T_g$ of the cooperativity plot, can be used to calculate the activation energy (E_a) of the glass transition using an Arrhenius relationship through the following set of equations ([6]).

$$S = -T_g \left[\frac{d \log a_T}{dT} \right]_{T_g} = \left[\frac{d \log a_T}{d(T/T_g)} \right]_{T_g} \quad (2)$$

$$E_a = 2.303RT_g S \quad (3)$$

The current study will focus on the applicability of cooperativity in characterizing the interfacial properties of basalt fibre reinforced epoxy composites. One interesting goal of characterizing composites interphases by cooperativity could be the use of a non-destructive experimental technique, DMA, with representative material samples, unlike in other micromechanical tests such as pull-out or microdebonding. These latter techniques are used to determine the interfacial shear stress (IFSS) from a microdopplet pull-out or debonding from a monofilament surface and use to give rise to high scatter results. However, DMA and cooperativity analysis use to be reproducible analysis methods. Hence, three types of basalt fibre reinforced epoxy composites will be analyzed: composites with 30 % wt of basalt fibre in the longitudinal direction, composites with 70 % wt of basalt fibre in the longitudinal direction and composites with 70 % wt of basalt fibre in the transversal direction. And each of the composite materials will have different surface treatments: original sized surface (OBF), unsized surfaces (UBF) and γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane treated surfaces (ABF). The effectiveness of cooperativity on analysing the interphase region of composites with different fibre weight fractions and testing orientations is going to be evaluated.

2 MATERIALS

The basalt fibre fabric used was a woven unidirectional plain sized to be compatible with epoxy resins, supplied by Basaltex NV (Wevelgem, Belgium) and named BAS UD 280.1350.P. Its surface density was 280 g/cm² with 90% of the fibres oriented in the warp direction with a diameter of 20 μm , and the other 10% of the fibres oriented in the weft direction with a diameter of 10 μm .

The basalt fibres composites have been studied with 3 different sizing natures: with the original sizing (OBF), unsized (UBF), and sized with γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane (ABF), obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. In order to apply a new coupling agent to basalt fibres the original sizing from OBF fibres have been removed immersing the plains in an acetone bath for 6 h at room temperature and

washing them in distilled water at constant stirring three times each. This unsized plains (UBF) were first oven-dried at 60°C for 3 days and then at 100°C for 3 h. This process was followed by the γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APS) coupling agent application onto the basalt fibre surface. The surface treatment was carried out with a silane-water solution in a concentration of 1% by weight. Basalt fibre plains were immersed into silane solutions and allowed to react for 2 h. The solution was then removed and the basalt fibres were washed first with water and then with ethanol, with the aim of removing unreacted molecules. Finally, the basalt fibres were dried in a furnace first at 60 °C for 3 days and then at 100 °C for 15 min.

Bisphenol-A type epoxy resin (D.E.R.TM 331TM, from The Dow Chemical Company) and its hardener (4,4'-Diamine-diphenylmethane (DDM), from Sigma-Aldrich) were used as matrix system (EP) with a stoichiometric mixture ratio (1:1).

Epoxy based composites reinforced with unidirectional basalt fibres were manufactured by compression moulding process with different fibre weight fractions (30 and 70 % wt.). The obtained laminates were then machined to the required micro-mechanical test samples dimensions in a FIDIA HS 644 milling machine.

3 TECHNIQUES

3.1 Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis

The composites were tested in a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (Rheometrics RSA-II) along and transvers to the fibre direction. The samples were analysed using the three point bending mode at a constant frequency of 1 Hz in a temperature region from 30 to 220 °C at a heating rate of 2 °C/min. In addition, frequency sweep measurements were performed at temperatures of 150, 160, 165, 170, 175, 180, 185, 190, 195, 200, 205, 210, 215, and 220 °C for a frequency range between 0.01 and 10 Hz. A minimum of two specimens, of 30x10x2 mm and 30x10x2.5 mm dimensions for 30% wt composites and 30x10x2.5 mm for 70% wt composites respectively, were tested for each sample.

3.2 Intermolecular cooperativity model

The time-temperature-superposition (TTS) procedure was used to construct master curves of the storage modulus (E') in the frequency domain for each of the samples studied. The glass transition temperatures, taken as the peak maximum of the $\tan\delta$ curves at 1 Hz, were used as the reference isotherms. Horizontal shift factor (a_T) values were obtained from the generation of the E' master curves and cooperativity plots were constructed by plotting $\log a_T$ against $(T/T_g)/T_g$ following the analysis of Plazek and Ngai [6]. The experimental data were then fit to Eq. (1) and the coupling constants were determined together with the steepness index (S) and the activation energies (E_a).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The dynamic storage modulus curves (E') obtained at 1 Hz for the composite samples and non-reinforced matrix are illustrated in Figure 1. It can be evidenced that basalt fibre incorporation significantly increases the modulus of the epoxy resin. The effect of increasing modulus is more pronounced in the rubbery response region at temperatures above the glass transition temperature (T_g). The differences in glassy and rubbery modulus onto each batch could be attributed to a slight fibre volume fraction deviations [8]. Nevertheless, noticeable modulus increase is observed for longitudinal 70% fibre content in weight composites (70L) comparing with transversal 70% fibre

content in weight (70T) and longitudinal 30% fibre content in weight (30L) composites, which show similar glassy and rubbery behaviour.

Furthermore, the glass-to-rubber transition regions of composite samples are smaller than in the neat epoxy matrix. Considering that the glass transition temperatures of the composites, defined by the peak maximum of the $\tan\delta$ curve and summarized in Table 1, are very close to each other and according to Deng et al. [9] who suggested that DMA is not sensitive to the variation of fibre-matrix adhesion due to the minimum or non-existent fibre/matrix debonding induced. A cooperativity analysis of the interfacial molecular mobility was carried out in order to yield better viscoelastic response of the composite than a direct comparison of DMA results, E' , E'' and $\tan\delta$.

Figure 1: Storage modulus curves for basalt fibre reinforced composites as well as non-reinforced epoxy resin.

The normalized E' master curves for all composite materials are illustrated in Figure 2. In the case of composites with 30% wt of fibre and analysed in the longitudinal direction (30L) no differences are observed in the master curves of composites with different sizings. In contrast, for the cases of composites with 70% wt of fibre analysed in both directions, longitudinal and transversal (70L and 70T, respectively), significant differences are noticed; especially in the case of ABF-70L and ABF-70T. These latter extends the glass-to-rubber transition zone to lower frequencies, or longer times, than the other two composites (OBF-70L and UBF-70L; and OBF-70T and UBF-70T). Regarding OBF and UBF samples, it can be observed that those analysed longitudinally shows noticeable differences from those analysed transversely. OBF-70T and UBF-70T show a very similar behaviour while OBF-70L shift to lower frequencies than UBF-70L. For longitudinal samples ABF-70L shows the slowest glass-to-rubber transition followed by OBF-70L and UBF-70L.

The cooperativity of the composite samples, based upon the E' data, clearly varies depending on the sizing used to treat the fibres (Figure 3 and Table 1). 70L and 70T composites show the same behaviour pattern. Namely, ABF have the steepest slopes, therefore the highest E_a , and the highest coupling parameter values. This implies strong mobility constriction produced by the basalt fibres on the polymer, which leads to higher temperature dependence for a segmental motion and

therefore higher energies. ABF is then followed by OBF and UBF, being this latter the composite with the poorest interphase region with the lowest S , E_a and n values.

Figure 2: Normalized storage modulus master curves obtained from DMA analysis of unidirectional laminates containing differently sized basalt fibres (a) longitudinal 30% in weight of fibre composites; (b) longitudinal 70% in weight of fibre composites and (c) transversal 70% in weight of fibre composites.

Figure 3: Cooperativity plots with the fit lines of Eq. 1 at temperature above T_g of unidirectional laminates containing differently sized basalt fibres (a) longitudinal 30% in weight of fibre composites; (b) longitudinal 70% in weight of fibre composites and (c) transversal 70% in weight of fibre composites.

Figure 4: Cross-sectional photographs of DMA (a) 30L and (b) 70L samples detailing fibre and matrix distribution geometry inside the composite.

Sample	T _g (°C)	C1	C2	S	E _a (KJ/mol)	n
<i>OBF-30L</i>	180	6.22	0.203	85.66	741	0.21
<i>UBF-30L</i>	181	5.55	0.183	65.39	569	0.11
<i>ABF-30L</i>	182	5.90	0.201	76.05	658	0.16
<i>OBF-70L</i>	185	6.68	0.262	80.43	703	0.28
<i>UBF-70L</i>	186	5.98	0.226	69.56	629	0.18
<i>ABF-70L</i>	185	9.73	0.630	91.92	815	0.56
<i>OBF-70T</i>	180	6.03	0.150	99.41	866	0.19
<i>UBF-70T</i>	180	6.00	0.158	92.87	815	0.18
<i>ABF-70T</i>	182	6.60	0.168	121.92	1056	0.30

Table 1: Glass transition temperature, T_g, WLF constants, C1 and C2, steepness index, S, activation energy, E_a, and coupling parameter, n, of differently sized basalt fibre/epoxy composites.

The 30L composites behaviour is rather singular. It was expected that they would show no differences between the samples or at the most a similar behaviour to that of the 70T composites. For 30L composites OBF shows the most strong interphase region with the highest S, Ea and n values comparing with UBF-30L and ABF-30L. In order to understand the possible causes of this behaviour the cross-section pictures of 30L and 70L samples were obtained by a NIKON SMZ745T stereoscopic microscope (Figure 4). 30L composite shows a heterogeneous material geometry unlike 70L composites, which shows better fibre/matrix distribution. This kind of heterogeneities could give rise to erratic. These measurements if directly used to construct the master curves and cooperativity plots will lead to erroneous material behaviour interpretations.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The viscoelastic response has been explored for basalt fibre reinforced epoxy composites with different fibre sizings and fibre weight fractions. Time-temperature superpositioning was successfully applied to the composite materials to construct master curves of the storage modulus in the frequency domain. The temperature dependence of the logarithmic shift factors, cooperativity, was found to vary with fibre sizing being sensitive enough to detect any change in the interphase region for basalt fibre reinforced epoxy composites. This model is a quantitative viscoelastic analysis rather than a qualitative analysis. The results obtained are reproducible except for 30L composites due to material geometry heterogeneities, which are difficult to be improved by a compression moulding process. Thus, pressed composite samples should have high fibre weight fraction in order to obtain reliable cooperativity results. From the cooperativity studies of composites with 70% wt of fibre, in both directions, clear differences are observed among the samples with different fibre treatments. ABF composites show the strongest mobility restriction leading to a better fibre/matrix adhesion, or interphase. Unlike UBF (unsized fibres) composites that as expected exhibit the weakest interphase.

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